

EEl: Atacama Extreme Environments Inhabitation Workshop: Native Materials

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Abstract

Extreme environments enable harnessing the capabilities of digital fabrication the most. During the three weeks EEl Workshop in 2017, a group of students and instructors explored how to fabricate with native materials in the extreme environment of the Atacama Desert in Chile. Universal Projects (UP), the workshop organizers, proposed the exercise of designing a research centre that would last for one year for four scientists. Material supply processing onsite was requested, for minimizing material transportation and cost. Currently underdeveloped in Fab Labs, incorporating material processing contributes to further bypass the mass production supply chain and increase sustainability. Further, I developed the *process design* concept to teach students about developing the processes and operations to digitally fabricate buildings in extreme environments. Material production, assembly and disassembly, were questioned for designing a circular economy building enabled by digital fabrication. The students proposed clay topo-bricks blocks without casting or mortar, printed by a Delta 3D Printer that will self-destruct when internal salt channels would grow into crystals. The workshop produced relevant research lines that many of our students have followed through afterwards. Through the *process design* conceptual framework, we developed basic material fabrication protocols generalizable to other EEl. By this, we seek to contribute to fabricate resilience for earth's most fragile ecologies.

Keywords: Native Materials, Fabrication, Atacama Desert, Circular Economy, Extreme Environments

Figure 1: N3ST Habitat, developed for NASA 3D Printing Challenge, by Universal Projects (2015), used as an example for the EEl Atacama 2017.

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1 Introduction

Gershenfeld (2012, 2018), states that Digital Fabrication (DF) will foster a revolution by allowing everyone to produce physical objects on demand, wherever and whenever they need them. This is particularly relevant when humans seek to inhabit extreme environments. In this context, the ideology of DF is expected to be critically questioned in order to democratize its impact, as Kohtala (2016) states.

Is in extreme environments, such as the Atacama Desert, where DF is unmistakably effective and most of its aforementioned capabilities are exploited. As early as in 2009, the US National Institute of Health suggested that in remote places, on demand production of medical instruments could be produced with additive manufacturing technologies (“Manufacturing Processes of Medical Technologies”, 2009). DF enables researchers and inhabitants of extreme and remote locations to have flexibility, improvisation, and customization through on demand production. On demand production on site enables the reduction of objects that need to be transported to site. The reduction of transportation also reduces the pollution produced by human activity. This aspect is particularly important for extreme environments such as Atacama, because of the fragility of the ecology, where every object needs to be transported in and out of the desert.

Yet, one the main limitations of DF are the material supply, especially in extreme environments. Global south construction processes are highly dominated by mass production, generating an unnecessary dependence on material suppliers. Transportation of material supply often increases the cost of implementing fabrication laboratories in general, turning this technology into a luxury. Furthermore, in extreme and remote locations such as the Atacama Desert, the dependence of commercially available material supplies increases the risk of turning Fab Labs into not sustainable enterprises. When transported to the Atacama Desert, the material cost can increase by three to five times its rate. To solve this material supply problem, we propose to incorporate a native material system into the digital fabrication process.

In the context of the EEI Workshop, we proposed to develop a material system with native raw materials for digitally fabricating a building in the Atacama Desert extreme environment. The material system was to be incorporated in the fabrication system. The system’s goal is reducing transportation and costs of constructing buildings. To generate a general framework that encompassed several production processes I developed the concept of Process Design (PD). PD urged the students of the EEI Atacama Workshop to think about means, processes and systems inscribed in fabrication. The EEI workshop approach promoted the idea of autonomous fabrication systems based on native raw materials, generalizable to Fab Labs.

2 Related Work

Relevant previous experiences with Material Systems exploration and digital fabrication include the work of Kayser (2011). The researcher has built a 3d Printer machine that uses sunlight and sand to make glass objects in the desert (“The Solar Sinter by Markus Kayser,” 2011). His work has sought to create an autonomous system by implementing material, fabrication and energy processing machines. In comparison with the presented work, Kayser goes one step further through energy production. In 2014, a “40-foot tower made of living fungus bricks” won the MOMA New York contest PS1. This tower was the first proof of the potential encompassed by fungus as a construction material (“Fungus Tower”, WIRED, 2104). The fungus bricks production does not include DF, but shows the potential of non standard materials incorporated in construction. Fungus has recently been used for DF as well in smaller scale projects (“Mycelium Printing and mold making – Digital Fabrication,” n.d.). Going back to the context of DF, local algae has been used to develop 3D printing filament in the Netherlands, and tested with producing designer kitchenware (“Dutch Designers Create Eco-Friendly Filament Using Dried Algae & Seaweed,” 2017).

Another interesting experience developed by Universal Projects members is BIEM. The BIEM is an initiative that replaces the plastic suppliers of artisanal fishery for those created from mycelia, algae,

and Agro forestry waste. The project is a partnership amongst *Bio fabrication Laboratory FADEU* (Catholic University of Chile), *LABVA Bio fabrication laboratory of Valdivia* (Chile) and *Synthetic Biology Lab* (Catholic University of Chile). Two specific supplies developed from biomaterials: *Buoys*, from mycelium of native fungi, and *Biofibers*, tensile fibbers for fishing nets, composed of biopolymers such as alginate (from brown algae), calcium carbonate (from molluscs) and chitin (from crustaceans).

Reducing the ecological impact of the construction process was proposed in the EEI Workshop exercise. Relevant to this approach is the work of Agustí-Juan (2017) by presenting a Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) method for design-integrated environmental assessment, to reduce the impact of DF in the environment. Such method does not question material production, however. Garmulewicz et al (2018) and several other researchers have proposed to use local recycled materials for DF, such as plastic and waste. Kohtala (2015), in an extensive literature review about the approach taken by DF researchers towards sustainability have presented relevant concepts and practices. "Key themes in the review included how distributed production can promote product longevity and closed material loops, as well as localizing production" (Kohtala, p.654, 2015).

2.1 Process Design

The concept of Process Design was developed as a comprehensive approach for designing the processes and operations to digitally fabricate a building in a specific environment. The main goal was including the material system, technologies, and the context as temporal variables of the design problem. Generally PD is aimed for directly designing processes in opposition of design objects. The concept of process design is more commonly used in Chemical engineering, but its definition is properly applicable for construction. According to Wikipedia, "PD is the choice and sequencing of units for desired physical and/or chemical transformation of materials...The design starts at a conceptual level and ultimately ends in the form of fabrication and construction plans" ("Process design," 2018). Read (2018) has defined Process Design as material flows, lead timing, factory floor coordination, and adds *Process Management*, for controlling job status and similar tasks. The temporality, considered as sequencing becomes relevant, and contextual acknowledgment, considered as environmental factors that affect the processes of the design.

Beorkrem (2017) explained a material focused approach, and have stated, "process-based design has become an accepted method for the conceptual development of architectural form", as in digital fabrication as well (p.7, 2017). The concept of PD also shares aspects with Menges' (20017) Computational Morphogenesis definition of material systems for architecture and fabrication.

Further, the concept of PD refers to the technological dimension that Brunelleschi incorporated into the design of the Santa Maria di Fiore Cupola. Brunelleschi's famous cupola for the cathedral of Florence was among the very first examples of this (design) technological dimension. As Picon and Ponte (20013) write, it is well known that Brunelleschi designed not only a structure but also the machines and the process that enabled its realization. This technological dimension talks about the necessary means for achieving a design, and not only designing the object itself.

PD framework has been defined to incorporate the environment as a variable of the design as well. Pallasmaa (1993) writes: 'Ecological architecture also implies a view of building more a process than a product...' (As cited in Beorkrem, p. 8, 2017). By this, the territory in which the fabrication process happens is incorporated into the design problem. Two dimensions are included, the impact of the fabrication process in the environment, and the impact of the environment in the fabrication process. Kohtala (2017) has referred to this idea as situated fabrication. One example is how the students incorporated climatic conditions into the process design, as speculatively using the morning fog to slowly grow salt crystals inside of the clay bricks.

Finally, the general goals of the approach developed for the EEI Atacama are to broaden the impact of digital fabrication by including native and local materials into the process/system, and to teach students about the architectural approach of designing with the environment, as circular economy. In

the case of the EEI Atacama PD, we questioned the processes that constitute the LCA of the building consisting of material production, assembly and disassembly, evaluating the means and the temporality of such stages.

3 EEI Atacama

3.1 Workshop Summary

The EEI had the participation of six graduate students from MIT, five from the Catholic University of Chile (PUC), and three from Chile University (U). My role was as professor in charge, MIT Student Jimmie Harris as teacher assistant, teaching in collaboration with the instructors Anibal Fuentes and Jose Hernandez from PUC. The Workshop was funded by MIT MISTI Chile, coordinated at the time by Erika Korowin. The EEI workshop included lectures from all the professors involved in the process. MIT Professor Skylar Tibbitts participated in the post-field work review when the students presented their observations and general proposal. Professors (MIT) Caitlin Mueller, (PUC) Pedro Alonso, and (PUC) Rodrigo Perez De Arce, participated in the final review of the EEI Atacama workshop. The EEI workshop was organized by Universal Projects¹, MIT, PUC Architecture School and Centro Del Desierto PUC.

The EEI workshop was based in Santiago, Chile, and included a visit to the Atacama Desert-- home of mining operations, astronomical observatories, informal settlements, and tests for Martian colonization. We spent one week in the dessert understanding the local conditions of Atacama and two weeks of design and prototyping in Santiago. While in Atacama we stayed at the PUC Punta Patache Research Centre. Students observed; how to obtain materials on site, how to build, how does people live in this areas, how isolation affect humans. They also evaluated what are the advantages of digital fabrication for this context. While in Santiago, we worked in the design of the four types of deliverables as part of a general process; a material system, a production technology, an inhabitation structure, and a settlement. A Delta Ceramic 3D printer was built by the team, led by Jimmie Harris to test native materials. Due to the short duration of the EEI the proposed processes are speculative, and the material system will be validated in further research. Following, I present the assignment statement guiding the student design exercise.

¹ **Universal Projects (UP)** is a company of architecture, design and development of technologies, oriented to create solutions to the most pressing challenges to human civilization. Our work is structured in five interconnected areas -Urban Informatics, Food Systems, Settlements, Human Augmentation and Material Systems- in order to embrace these challenges from a holistic perspective. UP was founded in Santiago de Chile in 2016 by seven architects interested in science and technology [Alejandro Weiss (PUC), Juan Pablo Ugarte (Harvard), Paloma Gonzalez (MIT), Jose Miguel Armijo (PUC-Perkin Eastman DUBAI) and Anibal Fuentes (PUC) who is the president of UP] and counts with collaborators from different disciplines. Between our achievements we count to be finalists on the NASA's 3D-Printed Habitat Challenge on 2015 with our project N3ST and finalists on the Biomimicry Global Design Challenge 2016 with our project SLANT. We also developed the EEI's and BIEM.

Figure 2: PUC Alto Patache Research Centre, main site for the Atacama trip and Design Exercise.

3.2 EEI Atacama Workshop Assignment Statement

Throughout a set of assignments, we will use inhabitation constraints presented by NASA (2015) in the Mars 3D-Printed Habitat Challenge Phase one. Incremental exercises will build upon the design of a dwelling for four explorers at the Alto Patache Station, in the Atacama Desert. This structure should accommodate its four users during a whole year in approximately in 1000 ft² (93 m²). Consequently, the facility needs to include cooking areas, sleeping quarters, and bathroom facilities, among other. Possible occupants are geologists, scientists, biologists, and engineers, who are expected to be considered while creating this structure. The unit should also be able to grow in time, and should have embedded on it the logic to produce larger aggregations and, eventually, a small settlement. On top of this, we will design the actual process of fabrication and construction of the individual structure and the larger settlement. This implies thinking on the material systems and proceses involved in its materialization, the technologies required for its fabrication and construction, and how all of them fit into existing (and possible decaying) networks transportation and flows of material, energy, and capital.

Students worked in groups to produce the following outcomes:

- *A material system to be employed in the construction of the whole dwelling unit, or part of it.*
- *A production technology (i.e. a machine) able to interface the material system and convert it into architectural components or elements.*
- *An inhabitation structure that deals with the challenges of inhabitation in extreme environments from a human factors perspective.*

- *A settlement for extreme environments that expands on the logic of the dwelling unit, and deals with the challenges inherent to a larger-scale complex.*

Context: Extreme Environments Constraints

*Constraints are often seen as a limitation rather than as an opportunity for design innovation. In most contexts of architectural production, the main constraint is budget. Budget has traditionally been considered to be correlated to the quality of architectural artefacts. Yet, such notion has been openly contested. A prime example of the latter case is Alejandro Aravena's (2012) incremental social projects. The budgetary restrictions of social housing are embedded in the building: Aravena designs the half of a good house instead of a full mediocre one, expecting that the inhabitants would build the second half. The goal of the EEI dwelling structure and settlement in Alto Patache is to shelter human beings in **Atacama Desert**, under extreme environmental, climatic, and human conditions. Highly oscillating temperatures, scarcity of weather, extreme sun radiation, earthquakes, and occasional flash floods are some of the characteristics that make this desert an extreme environment. Consequently, the main constraints in this domain will be to provide protection from the environment, and to engage with the site's geographic particularities in synergic ways. Furthermore, a consequent constraint is to protect an extreme environment from human influenced changes.*

Context: Onsite Native Materials and Digital Fabrication

Due to the geographical remoteness that characterizes them, building in extreme environments is inherently difficult and risky. The transportation of large volumes of material, prefabricated components, and/or large machinery is expensive at best, and unsustainable and practically impossible at worst. Taking this into consideration, the dwelling outpost has to be built using mainly local materials, and semi-autonomous 3D-printing technologies that can be deployed on-site with ease. By observing the materials that are abundant in the desert such as regolith, clay, sand, salt, rocks, and copper and other minerals; and by obtaining inspiration from local geological and biological morphogenetic processes. Students will think of ways of building in the desert using locally available resources. The constraints in this domain were to use local materials as much as possible and to use fabrication and construction 3D-printing machinery easy to transport and deploy onsite.

Context: Inhabitation in Extreme Environments

Living for extended periods of times in extreme and hostile environments affects the human body, mind, and spirit in ways that are often difficult to anticipate. Due to the challenges of building in these contexts, the structures that are deployed for that purpose are often too small, to unwelcoming, and too foreign from what people tend to consider comfortable. Moreover, these constructions need to address a series of challenges that traditional living do not: energy self-sufficiency and efficiency, need of repeated maintenance, etc. Several examples illustrate this extreme inhabitation condition such as space stations, submarines, remote lighthouses, Antarctic research facilities, mountain refuges, etc. The constraint in this domain is perhaps more open and ambiguous than the previous ones: to respond to the condition of extremeness from the perspective of human factors, i.e. how what the dwellers do and how they do it will affect the design of the structure.

Context: Process Design

Design the processes, the technology, the workflow, the temporality of the buildings. Design the Material Production, Assembly and Disassembly, Circular Economy and Life Cycle of the building.

Figure 3: EEI Students and Instructors. Ammar Ahmed, Pakistan, MIT; Blanca Valdes, Chile, PUC; Prof. Anibal Fuentes, Chile, PUC; Prof. Paloma Gonzalez, Chile, MIT; Stefano Rossi, Chile, PUC; Jose Vilches, Chile, UChile; Juan Pablo Meniconi, Chile, UChile; Seung Woo Han, Korea, PUC; Luis Mosquera, Chile, UChile; Cristobal Burgos, Chile, PUC; Ricardo Walker, Chile, PUC; Noora Aljabi, USA, MIT; Xhulio Binjaku, USA, MIT; Jimmie Harris, USA, MIT; Cristina Clow, USA, MIT; MyDung Thi Nguyen, USA, MIT; and Catherine Lie, Indonesia, MIT.

3.3 Final Project: Patache Research Center Process Design

As a PD framed project, the students designed the processes that constitute the lifecycle of the building. Material production, assembly and disassembly achieved a circular economy building. The material production included finding the locations to extract the materials and processing them. The Atacama Desert is an extensive source of native materials the students took advantage of, such as clay, calcium carbonate, and salt. The extraction was defined as simply digging of the soil, limited by the constraint of not affecting the environment. The use of native materials was meant to ensure a better response to climate. Students observed natural phenomenon of the environment such as natural clay formations and when salt grows inside clay and limestone rocks and breaks them apart in time. The material production was designed to happen on site and using contextual conditions.

In addition to native material, the use of 3D printing production technology enabled the students to propose clay topo-bricks blocks without casting or mortar, printed by the Delta 3D Printer on site. Topo-bricks geometry reduces assembly efforts as the shape secures the joining (Dyskin, Pasternak, & Estrin, 2012). Topo-bricks are reused if needed, in the case of building a settlement. Further, material production processes in the desert are affected by weather conditions such as cold nights, hot days, and mornings with mist. As a response the students decided to include salt-micro-channels in the topo-bricks, and use mist in their favour to harvest the salt as growing crystals that destroy the blocks in time. The self-destroying process goal was to leave a minimum ecological footprint and reduce disassembly efforts. Designing the lifecycle building process promoted a circular economy approach on the fragile ecology of the Atacama Desert.

The inhabitation structure is composed by chambers for basic human activities, a fog catcher to obtain water and a sewage treatment area. If after the year that the research centre should last, researchers decide to stay, a settlement will be established following the skyline of the hills. The shape of the chamber was designed to function as positive pressure ventilation. The foundations of the building will be composed by used tires found in the desert. A piping system will carry water from fog catchers distributed in the hills. Once the Research Centre would be unoccupied, neighbours will be prompted to still the structural elements of the settlement. The student proposed these ideas to contribute to the communities that are currently part of the environment of the Atacama Desert.

Figure 4: Sketches of bricks with salt micro channels. In a temporal process the salt will absorb the moisture in time and will build salt crystals that will grow and destroy the bricks.

Figure 5: Material testing; clay, Calcium Carbonate, Salt and Lime stone. Students investigated how to produce the material by combining the ingredients and also how to dissolve the bricks with water.

Figure 7: Topological interlocking bricks used for the final project.

Figure 8: Material processing testing with the Delta 3D Printer, built by Jimmie Harris and I. The last image shows one of the topo-bricks tests with the machine.

Figure 9: Inhabitation structure: first image is a section of the tunnel-shaped dwellings, second image shows how the building works with humidity, and finally the foundations of the dwelling will be built with up cycled tires.

Figure 10: Process Design of the Inhabitation Structure

Figure 11 Disappearance of the inhabitation structure

Figure 12: Final Project.

3.4 EEI Basic Protocols

After the EEI workshop UP members developed basic material protocols for extreme environment inhabitation. The material sources for digital fabrication have been evaluated in terms of 4 general parameters: properties, availability, processing ease, and environment viability. The parameter to evaluate these protocols is a conservative approach towards all resources. Material **properties** refer to construction mechanical properties. The availability is measured in terms of abundant presence of the material source. **Processing ease:** process must be possible onsite and with basic and/or minimal equipment. **Environmental viability:** basically means to minimize human impact on the environment, through extraction and material processing.

4 Discussion

Proposing to include onsite material systems as part of the DF workflow is one of the contributions of this paper. The use of native and local materials contributes for Fab Labs to bypass the supply chain and mass production. Through this, Fab Labs will be closer to achieve their ultimate goal; to democratize production, as stated by Kohtala (2016).

In the context of EEI Atacama, DF was questioned in terms of its advantages; *why should we use DF?* Extreme environments constrain the supply of resources; the advantages of DF are reducing workforce and producing refined shapes, enhancing the construction process.

The EEI Workshop lasted only three weeks and was an intense hands-on educational experience. This experience did not comprise a lengthy period to fully validate all the ideas that we included in it. For example, the EEI workshop did not include the validation of the topo-bricks and the salt-channels, which is expected to do in further research. Our goal in this educational instance was to question construction processes and production, to critically think digital fabrication in the context of extreme environments, and to elaborate Process Design research lines that expand current design education.

Process Design fabrication framework was developed and presented to contribute to the general workflow of DF. The goal is to develop a theoretical approach that eases thinking in how the fabrication stages are expected to be developed. Considering the fabrication workflow as a process and not as the production of an object is expected to promote critical thinking and the inclusion of the temporal dimension of the process. PD seeks to incorporate the means of production such as the material system, the technology, and the reciprocal connection with the environment.

The contributions of this paper are: presented the EEI Atacama workshop with the use of native materials in DF, developed initial protocols for DF material production in Extreme Environments, and conceptualized the Process Design framework DF workflow, including the incorporation of material supply processing as part of the Fab Lab to bypass mass production and increase the ecological impact of digital fabrication.

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